

THE ALMOST PRESUMABLE MAXIMALITY OF SOME TOPOLOGICAL LEMMA

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Abstract

Some splitting lemma of topological nature provides fundamental information when dealing with dynamics (see [1], pg.79). Because the set involved, namely $X \setminus \mathcal{P}_s$, is neither open nor closed, a natural question arise: can this set be modified in order to obtain additional data ? Unfortunately, the answer is negative.

For a metric space X which is locally connected and locally compact and for some continuous mapping $f : X \rightarrow X$, the set ω -set of each element x of X is given by the formula

$$\omega(x) = \left\{ y \in X \mid y = \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} f^{k_n}(x), \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} k_n = +\infty \right\}.$$

We also denote by $\omega_j(x)$, $1 \leq j \leq r$, the set

$$\omega_j(x) = \left\{ y \in X \mid y = \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} f^{m_n \cdot r + j}(x), \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} m_n = +\infty \right\}.$$

Now, $\omega(x)$ can be splitted according to the following lemma.

Lemma 1 a) $\omega(x) = \bigcup_{j=1}^r \omega_j(x)$;

b) $f(\omega_j(x)) \subset \omega_{(j+1) \bmod r}$.

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Its proof relies upon the properties of $\omega(x)$.

Lemma 2 For some nonvoid subset S of X we consider C a component of $X \setminus S$, i.e. a maximal connected set (see [2], pg. 54). Then:

a) $\overline{C}^X \subset C \cup (S \cap \partial^X S)$:

b) $\partial^X C \subset (C \cap \partial^X C) \cup (S \cap \partial^X S)$,

where $\overline{C}^X$ signifies the closure of C under the topology of X while $\partial^X C$ is the boundary of C under the same topology.

Remark 1 For instance, if S is closed, then $\partial^X C \subset \partial^X S$ as the components of a locally connected space are open.

Proof. a) First, let's show that $\overline{C}^X \subset C \cup S$. For $x \in X \setminus (C \cup S) = (X \setminus S) \setminus C$, as C is closed in $X \setminus S$, there will be some open $G \subset X$ such that

$$x \in G \cap (X \setminus S) \subset X \setminus (C \cup S).$$

Obviously,

$$[G \cap (X \setminus S)] \cap C = G \cap C = \emptyset$$

and so

$$x \notin \overline{C}^X.$$

Further on, let's assume that $x \in \overline{C}^X \cap S$. If $x \in X \setminus \partial^X S$, then $x \notin \overline{X \setminus S}^X$. There will be some open $W \subset X$ such that

$$x \in W ; W \cap \overline{X \setminus S}^X = \emptyset.$$

In particular, $W \cap C = \emptyset$ and so $x \notin \overline{C}^X$.

b) According to a), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{C}^X \cap \overline{X \setminus C}^X &= \partial^X C \subset (C \cap \overline{X \setminus C}^X) \cup [(S \cap \partial^X S) \cap \overline{X \setminus C}^X] \\ &= (C \cap \overline{X \setminus C}^X) \cup (S \cap \partial^X S) \end{aligned}$$

because of $S \cap \partial^X S \subset S \subset X \setminus C$.

Obviously,

$$C \cap \overline{X \setminus C}^X = (C \cap \overline{X \setminus C}^X) \cap \overline{C}^X = C \cap \partial^X C.$$

■

Remark 2 It worths noticing that the sets $(C \cap \partial^X C)$ and $(S \cap \partial^X S)$ are disjoint; in other words, $\partial^X C$ is piecewise-made. Lemma 2 works equally well in any topological space.

Lemma 3 (Melbourne, Dellnitz, Golubitsky)

For some nonvoid subset S of X , we denote by $\mathcal{P}_s$ the union

$$\mathcal{P}_s(f) = \bigcup_{n=0}^{\infty} (f^n)^{-1}(S)$$

Let x be some element of S . Then either $\omega(x) \subset \overline{\mathcal{P}_s^X}$ or the following are valid:

- a) $\omega(x) \setminus \mathcal{P}_s$ is covered by finitely many (connected) components $C_0, \dots, C_{\tau-1}$ of $X \setminus \mathcal{P}_s$;
- b) These components can be ordered so that $f(C_i) \subset C_{(i+1) \bmod \tau}$;
- c) $\omega(x) \subset \overline{C_0^X} \cup \dots \cup \overline{C_{\tau-1}^X}$.

Remark 3 Notice the splitting in relation with lemma 1. As we mentioned in the Abstract, it is quite natural to ask if $X \setminus \mathcal{P}_s$ can be replaced by the easier-to-work-with $X \setminus \overline{\mathcal{P}_s}$. The following lemma shows that this would imply no more the presence of finitely many components.

Lemma 4 Let S be some nonvoid subset of X which is not dense in X , i.e. $\overline{S^X} \neq X$. We consider C a component of $X \setminus \overline{S^X}$ and D a component of $X \setminus S$ such that $C \subset D$. Then any element x of $D \setminus C$ belongs either to $\partial^X S$ or to any other component of $X \setminus \overline{S^X}$.

Proof. If $x \notin X \setminus \overline{S}$ then $x \in (X \setminus S) \cap \overline{S^X} \subset \partial^X S$. ■

An example would be appropriate: in $\mathbf{R}^2$, we denote by $\mathcal{D}(0, r)$ the r -disk centered in 0. Now, for $X = \overline{\mathcal{D}(0, 2)^{\mathbf{R}^2}}$, $S = \mathcal{D}(0, 1) \cup (1, 2] \cup [-2, -1)$, we have

$$\overline{S^{\mathbf{R}^2}} = \overline{\mathcal{D}(0, 1)^{\mathbf{R}^2}} \cup [1, 2] \cup [-2, -1]$$

$$D = X \setminus S, C \in \left\{ \left(X \setminus \overline{S^{\mathbf{R}^2}} \right) \cap (y > 0), \left(X \setminus \overline{S^{\mathbf{R}^2}} \right) \cap (y < 0) \right\}.$$

Further exemples can be architected easily even to obtain infinitely many components of $X \setminus \overline{S^X}$.

In other words, finitely many components of $X \setminus S$ may include infinitely many components of $X \setminus \overline{S^X}$.

References

- [1] I. Melbourne, M. Dellnitz, M. Golubitsky, *The structure of symmetric attractors*, Arch. Rational Mech. Anal., 123, pp. 75-98, 1993
- [2] J. L. Kelley, *General topology*, D. Von Nostrand Comp., 1955